

Multiferroicity in Haldane chain based polycrystalline $R_2\text{BaNiO}_5$ ($R=\text{Tb, Sm}$)

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Abstract

The rare-earth (R) family, $R_2\text{BaNiO}_5$, crystallizing in an orthorhombic structure (space group: Immm), has been considered to be the first convincing example for Haldane spin-chain behavior and the spinchain anomalies arise from Ni ($S = 1$). While these compounds attracted considerable attraction over several years from the magnetism point of view, the highly insulating nature of these materials somehow escaped the attention of the community to search for magnetoelectric coupling effects. In the present work we have taken two system $R_2\text{BaNiO}_5$ ($R=\text{Tb, Sm}$) to explore its ferroelectric as well as magneto-electric effects. $\text{Tb}_2\text{BaNiO}_5$ has been known to order antiferromagnetically below ($T_N =$) 63 K. The present magnetic studies on the polycrystals bring out that there is another magnetic transition at a lower temperature ($T_2 =$) 25 K with pronounced magnetic-field-induced metamagnetic and metaelectric behaviors. Multiferroic features are found below T_2 . The most intriguing observation is that the magneto-dielectric effect is intrinsic and largest (e.g., $\sim 18\%$ at 15 K) within this Haldane spin-chain family $R_2\text{BaNiO}_5$. $\text{Sm}_2\text{BaNiO}_5$, which has been proposed to order antiferromagnetically around ($T_N =$) 55 K, was investigated for its complex dielectric permittivity, magnetodielectric and pyrocurrent behavior as a function of temperature (T). The pyrocurrent measured in the presence of a bias electric field as well as dielectric constant reveal a weak peak with increasing T around 22 K—the temperature around which population of the exchange-split excited state of Kramers doublet has been known to occur. This finding suggests that this compound presents a novel situation in which multiferroicity is induced by an interplay between crystal-field effects and exchange interaction.

Keywords: Haldane Chain, Multiferroicity, ferroelectric etc.

References:

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